

Rumble! Rumble! Voluntary vs. Acoustic Activation Reveal Similarities in two Middle Ear Muscle Reflex Activity

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ABSTRACT

About 43% of people can voluntarily contract their middle ear muscles, creating a "rumbling" sensation, typically driven by the tensor tympani (TTM). In contrast, the sound-evoked middle ear muscle reflex (MEMR) is dominated by the stapedius muscle (SM). This study aimed to separate the acoustic effects of the TTM and SM, and examine their interactions. Twenty-four normal-hearing adults who could voluntarily contract their middle ear muscles participated. We used a double-dissociation-like paradigm with two manipulations: (1) voluntary TTM activation in a go/nogo task, and (2) reflexive activation with varying stimulus levels (55/85 dB SPL). Band-limited (0.89-4.2 kHz) click trains were presented bilaterally to monitor and elicit reflex activation. Results showed that in the nogo/85 dB condition, 22/23 participants demonstrated strong MEMR activation, driven by the SM. In the go/55 dB condition, 16/23 participants showed TTM activation. All participants exhibited activation in the go/85 dB condition. These findings demonstrate that the TTM influences middle ear sound transmission. Complex, individualized patterns of muscle activity occur when both muscles are active. In the frequencies included in this study (1-4 kHz), the lack of statistical difference between nogo/85 and go/85 conditions would suggest that the SM may dominate the acoustic effects in the ear canal.

INTRODUCTION

The mammalian middle ear is a critical impedance matching system between the air-filled ear canal and the fluid-filled cochlea. This impedance matching is dominated largely the mechanics of the tympanic membrane the three ossicles, and supported by the physical characteristics of the tympanic cavity. The human middle ear also contains two muscles, the stapedius (SM) and the tensor-tympani (TTM), that influence the ossicular mechanics, often in opposing directions (Cho et al., 2023; Gallagher et al., 2021; Fournier et al., 2022). To what extent the muscles influence hearing has been debated since the 18th century. Particularly the SM is thought to play a protective role while also reducing the impact of upward spread of masking and attenuating self-generated noise (Borg, Counter, & Rosler, 1984). In addition, sound-evoked middle ear muscle reflex (MEMR) is thought to be dominated by the SM, producing a change in impedance characteristics of the middle ear in humans. This change can be measured non-invasively and serves as an economical and efficient audiological tool aiding in the diagnosis of retrocochlear pathology for decades (Metz, 1946). In contrast, the acoustic consequences as well as the functional relevance of the TTM is not fully understood. This is in part due to its relatively poor sensitivity to sound (Stach et al., 1984). Here we exploit the ability of some individuals (~43% of humans; Röddiger et al., 2021) to voluntarily activate the MEMR, called "rumblers", to study the acoustic consequences, including the dynamics, of TTM activation in comparison with the sound-evoked SM. We hypothesized that voluntary activation of the MEMR, i.e., by "rumbling", will invoke differential effects on the middle ear transfer function relative to the SM that is activated acoustically. This exploratory research could provide further insights in to how the TTM impacts the auditory system and may help identify functions of the TTM in humans.

METHOD

A. Participants

Twenty-four young adults (mean age: 22.48 years; 7 males) with clinically normal hearing participated in the study. Normal hearing was confirmed through otoscopy, behavioral thresholds <20 dB HL (0.25–8 kHz), and type-A tympanograms. Participants were recruited via posters titled “Can You Make Your Ears Rumble?” Tympanic membrane movement during voluntary middle ear muscle (MEM) contractions was confirmed using a video otoscope. Participants provided written informed consent. The study was approved by the University of Wisconsin-Madison Health Sciences Institutional Review Board. Prior to the experiment, participants completed a six-question survey on their ability to voluntarily produce ear rumbling. Questions assessed sound characteristics, perceived loudness (scale 1–5), lateralization, and techniques used to elicit the rumble.

B. Experimental set-up, stimulus, and paradigm

Bilateral clicks, individually flattened between 0.8–4.2 kHz using forward pressure level calibration, were digitally generated in MATLAB and delivered using the dual-probe ER10X system (Etymotic Research, IL, USA). Stimuli were presented at 55 and 85 dB peak-to-peak sound pressure level (ppSPL) to monitor MEMR activated through rumbling (low level) vs. acoustically (high level). Participants sat in a sound-attenuating booth and followed in-ear instructions to “rumble” or refrain in a randomized go/no-go paradigm. Go trials included voice prompts (“go” and “stop”). No-go trials used the phase-scrambled (incomprehensible) version of the same prompts to ensure equal stimulus energy exposure across conditions. Click trains at 80 Hz were presented for 2s between the voice prompts with 50 trials per condition for 85 dB ppSPL and 100 for 55 dB ppSPL.

C. Response analysis

Recorded ear canal pressures were bandpass filtered (0.7–5 kHz) and a median-based artifact rejection was applied. Click epochs with root-mean-squared (RMS) amplitude >2.25 times the interquartile range were excluded. Reflex presence was quantified using reverse pressure level (RPL) changes in seven 1/3-octave bands (1–4 kHz). To better visualize data, the 85 dB ppSPL clicks were scaled down to 55 dB ppSPL. RPL time series were fitted with a two-term exponential function and reflex magnitude was extracted from the fit for each participant. Responses were included if reflex magnitude increased with stimulus level and showed significant activation in at least 6 of the 7 frequency bands. One participant was excluded due to inconsistent responses.

RESULTS

A. Perceptual attributes of rumbling

All participants answered “yes” to being able to make their ears produce noise, meeting the inclusion criterion. Responses to the nature of the sound fell into two categories: (1) low-frequency noises such as vibration, rattle, rumble, buzzing, crackling, and whooshing, and (2) high-frequency ringing (reported by only one participant). Some provided analogies: (1) shaking sheet metal, (2) hearing underwater, (3) rapid drum beats, (4) distant avalanche or rocks, and (5) thunder. On the loudness of the rumbling sound, participants rated it an average of 2.6 on a 5-point scale, indicating it is audible but not overpowering. Nine of the 24 participants reported that one ear was louder than the other, with 4 of them selecting the right ear. Three participants reported they could rumble on demand by simply thinking about it, 7 used ear clenching or flexing, 5 squinted or tightly closed their eyes, 3 created pressure in their ear, mouth, or sinuses, and 6 felt it was similar to squinting or flexing their ear muscles, including the pinna in one case.

FIGURE 1. Violin plots showing the magnitude of stimulus change for the 7 frequency bands clustered and colored for three conditions nogo/85, go/55, and go/85. Median is the white circle, mean is the red horizontal line, and the colored vertical lines through the violins represent the data range.

B. Both rumbling and click stimulus activate the MEMR

As expected, participants demonstrated a change in click RPL for both rumbling (go) and stimulus (nogo) conditions. Of the 23 participants included in analyses, 16 (~70%) demonstrated a consistent change in the go/55 condition, where we expect only the TTM to be active. Ideally, given all participants were visually confirmed to be able to rumble, we expected 100% of the participants would demonstrate measurable change in click RPL. In contrast, 22/23 (~96%) of the participants demonstrated robust change in RPL for nogo/85, where only the SM is thought to be active. This is consistent with our prior reports of robust MEMR activation at 85 dB ppSPL (Boothalingam & Goodman, 2021; Boothalingam et al., 2021). When both rumbling and the click was present concurrently, i.e., the go/85 condition, all participants demonstrated robust MEMR activation. Finally, no participants demonstrated MEMR activation at nogo/55, as expected, where both the TTM and the SM were expected to be at rest/relaxed state. For this reason, the nogo/55 condition is not shown in any plots.

As seen in Fig. 1, the overall magnitude of stimulus change between go/55 (TTM-only; red), nogo/85 (SM-only; yellow), and go/85 (SM+TTM; purple) do not appear different. The slightly larger variability in go/55 could be attributed to (1) larger variability resulting from smaller SNR at the lower probe level (55 dB ppSPL), and (2) the scaling-down the 85 dB ppSPL earcanal pressures to 55 dB ppSPL may have reduced the size of the reflex magnitude. Both high level probe conditions, nogo/85 and go/85, where the SM and SM+TTM, respectively, are expected to be active appear to be overlapping in Fig. 2. With the exception of 1 and 1.3 kHz, the go/55 too seem similar to the other two conditions. Given the pattern of results does not appear to deviate from Fig. 1, where magnitude was extracted from individual fits to the raw stimulus change, it is unlikely that averaging the time-course affected the true time-course of reflex-mediated effects on the stimulus.

We applied two linear mixed effects models to test the statistical significance of these observations. In the first model, frequency was modeled as separate variable along with the three conditions (go55, nogo85, and go85) as fixed effects and participants as random effects on the stimulus change. This model showed no main effect of frequency ($F[1,430]=1.8$, $p=0.18$) or interactions between frequency and condition ($F[1,430]=1.9$, $p=0.17$). This model, however, revealed a slightly better outcome for the effect of condition ($F[1,430]=3.3$, $p=0.07$). To explore this further, in the second model, we averaged the stimulus change across frequencies to remove the frequency variable. This model revealed a significant main effect of condition ($F[1,61]=10.5$, $p=0.002$). Posthoc t-tests, corrected for multiple comparisons using Bonferroni correction revealed marginal significance in stimulus changes between TTM-only (go55) vs. SM-only (nogo85; mean difference = 0.08 dB; $t[21]=2.8$, $p=0.043$) and between TTM-only (go55) vs. SM+TTM (go85; mean difference = 0.08 dB; $t[21]=2.8$, $p=0.042$). The positive mean difference values suggest that the go55 (TTM-only) produced a larger change relative to both conditions where SM was present. This is, however, due to the scaling down of the stimulus, and therefore also the stimulus change from 85 to 55 dB ppSPL. Finally, there was no

FIGURE 2. Mean stimulus change across participants (filled circles) and two-term exponential fits to the mean change (lines) are plotted for the three conditions indicated by colors for the 7 $1/3^{rd}$ octave center frequencies (organized in separate panels).

difference between nogo/85 and go/85 conditions where any additive effects of TTM on SM would be expected in go/85 (mean difference = 0.001 dB; $t[21]=0.1$, $p=0.92$).

DISCUSSION

This exploratory study aimed to understand the acoustic effects of TTM contraction and its interactions with SM contractions, using voluntary TTM activation (rumblers) as a model. Our findings expand on existing knowledge by providing frequency-specific estimates of changes in sound pressure level (SPL) due to TTM activation. Unlike previous studies that used 226 Hz tones with clinical tympanometers, which only assessed TTM dynamics at low frequencies, we investigated TTM responses across 0.89-4.2 kHz and compared them with well-established SM effects and their interactions.

A. Stapedius muscle may dominate MEMR between 1-4 kHz

Previous studies have shown that TTM activation pulls the tympanic membrane inward, stiffening the ossicular chain and increasing middle ear static pressure (Aron et al., 2015; Fournier et al., 2022; Cho et al., 2023), and may also push the stapes into the cochlea (Fournier et al., 2022). In contrast, SM activation pulls the stapes away from the cochlea, antagonizing TTM motion. Our results suggest no significant differences in the magnitude of pressure changes across three conditions (see Figs. 1 and 2). This contrasts with the larger acoustic compliance changes reported by Aron et al. (2015) in cadaveric middle ear muscle manipulations. Similarly, Cho et al. (2023) observed greater velocity and phase changes at the umbo and stapes with manual TTM pulls versus SM pulls, especially below 1 kHz, using optical coherence tomography. Similar findings have been reported in gerbils (Gallagher et al., 2021) and guinea pigs (Nuttall, 1974) using laser Doppler vibrometry and cochlear microphonics, respectively. Using low probe frequencies (e.g., 226 Hz) likely yields greater differences in TTM vs. SM effects on ear canal pressure and related metrics like admittance. The lack of difference between go/85 and nogo/85 in our study may be due to our use of click probes band-limited between 0.89 and 4.2 kHz. We chose to use this frequency based on previously demonstrated

large effects of SM in the 1-3 kHz region (e.g., Feeney and Keefe, 1999). This may also explain that despite visual confirmation of rumbling, only 16/24 participants demonstrated significant stimulus change in the go/55 condition. Further studies should consider including lower frequencies to test whether the TTM dominates frequencies below 1 kHz.

If TTM and SM contractions have antagonistic effects on the ossicular chain, we would expect a detrimental effect when both are active (SM+TTM) compared to SM alone. Conversely, if their effects add in phase, an additive effect would be observed. In our group mean time-course (Fig. 2) and statistical tests, adding TTM (go/85) to the sound-evoked MEMR (nogo/85) did not produce noticeable changes, suggesting that SM may dominate the MEMR at the tested frequencies. However, individual data (Fig. 1) show a slight additive effect of TTM on SM, with some individuals showing large differences, though most centered around zero. A limitation of our study is the lack of a condition where SM is activated while TTM is already on. To test this, a dichotic stimulus would be needed, with 55 dB ppSPL click probes in one ear and 85 dB ppSPL elicitors in the other ear during active rumbling.

B. What causes the variability in perceived rumbling sound across individuals?

The dominant low-frequency effect of the TTM in the literature may explain the low-frequency rumbling and whooshing sounds reported by rumblers. The perceived loudness rating of 2.6 on our 5-point scale suggests these sounds could partly be due to the occlusion effect, which enhances internal bodily noises. Additionally, the TTM works closely with the tensor veli palatini muscle, responsible for opening and closing the Eustachian tube (Aristeguieta et al., 2010). Voluntary TTM activation could trigger a rush of air into the middle ear if the Eustachian tube opens due to pressure differences, potentially explaining the whooshing sound. Repeated Eustachian tube opening and closing might also account for the clicking sounds some rumblers report. Involuntary TTM activation (myoclonus) has been linked to objective tinnitus observable in tympanometry (Zipfel et al., 2000). Fournier et al. (2022) pitch-matched the low-frequency rumbling to around 30 Hz. In our visual examination, the tympanic membrane showed a gentle tug, likely oscillating at around 30 Hz, although our camera's 25 Hz frame rate may have limited our ability to detect higher frequencies due to aliasing. Whether the sound is caused by tympanic membrane flutter, occlusion, or Eustachian tube opening is still unclear and likely varies among individuals, explaining the perceptual differences in rumbling. Further studies should also explore the ability of individual to sustain rumbling vs. those who can only produce in repeated bursts to investigate whether a decay in TTM activation exists similar to the reflex decay measures of the SM.

C. Implications for hearing

In general, the hypothesized roles for the MEMR are (1) protection against loud noises, (2) improving speech SNR in noisy environments, and (3) reducing self-generated noise. However, the protective role is uncertain due to the reflex's delay in activation, making it ineffective for impulse noise. However, low-frequency attenuation offered by the MEMR may be effective against sustained noise, and may aid in reducing masking (Lieberman and Guinan, 1998). Given that middle ear muscles activate before speech (Borg and Zakrisson, 1974), TTM and SM have been posited to improve SNR in noisy conversations. However, given a significant proportion of self-generated speech reaches the cochlea via bone conduction, altered stiffness in the middle ear would have limited to no effect on the bone conducted sound. Despite working antagonistically, the combined effects of these muscles do influence sound transmission through the middle ear. This is certainly useful in auditory diagnostics. To what extent the middle ear muscles directly useful in hearing is still emerging. Recent discussions suggest the MEMR may also play a role in sound localization (Gallagher et al., 2021; Cho et al., 2023), with middle ear muscles potentially fine-tuning interaural time (ITD) and level differences (ILD). However, as TTM activation requires high sound levels, further research is needed to understand its benefits for sound localization. In animals with movable pinnae (e.g., cats), somatosensory activation of TTM/SM may improve localization.

CONCLUSION

This exploratory study aimed to differentiate the acoustic effects of the stapedius (SM) and tensor tympani muscle (TTM) using a double-dissociation-like paradigm, with both acoustic (involuntary) and voluntary activation. We hypothesized that the dynamics of the two muscles would differ, with TTM dominating voluntary activation and

SM dominating acoustic activation. Our findings suggest (1) more consistent activation for sound-evoked versus voluntary reflexes, (2) SM dominates MEMR effects between 1-4 kHz, and (3) the dynamics of both reflexes are similar (between 1-4 kHz) despite their antagonistic roles. These results contribute to the growing literature on the functional and physiological differences between the two middle ear muscles.

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COMMENTS & DISCUSSION

[**Jon Siegel**]: Why did you not look below 1 kHz because that is where the biggest effects of stiffness are and both muscles act to increase stiffness

[**Sriram Boothalingam, author**]: Great question. We were going by what we had previously done in the lab. Where, for high stimulus levels we tend to see big effects around 1 kHz. We thought we should be able to see the same kind of changes [in the stimulus]. In retrospect, I would have liked to include low frequencies. Also, we were playing clicks and calibrating it at the eardrum using FPL [to have flat spectrum] and we sometimes ran into problems where we could not flatten the clicks as we would run out of headroom [in the driver output]. So, we went with the frequency range to concentrate the energy between 0.8-4 kHz, and if we went for a much broader frequency we would have to settle with a lower stimulus level. But definitely, we should follow up with lower frequencies. Looks like there are quite a few rumblers [around] so we should be able to do it again.

[**Chris Bergevin**]: Sorry if I missed this. Did you ever see if there is an acoustic signature in the ear canals, if you stick an OAE probe and see when they are rumbling see what sort of sound comes back out

[**Sriram Boothalingam, author**]: Good question. This is what Shawn Goodman asked me too. To look at the noise floor. We have the data, but I have not looked at it yet. When we looked in the ear canals visually it did not seem like it [eardrum] was fluttering or moving. It was just as very gently tug on the eardrum. If it was doing anything fast, we could have missed it as our video otoscope was very low in frame rate. But looking at the noise floor to see if anything is going on would be good.

[**Ernst Dalhoff, session chair**]: You did not show any phase data. Are they showing basically the same?

[**Sriram Boothalingam, author**]: Good question. Some of the magnitude changes I am showing also include phase as we look at it in the complex domain. But we have looked at the time constants and it is very variable. Sometimes it is very low and sometimes it is at the [fit] bounds.

[**Ondrej Tichacek**]: The individuals described the sounds differently. Did you try to separate them by the groups? E.g., thunder, the shell to see if the effect within these groups?

[**Sriram Boothalingam, author**]: I did not, but we could do that. However, it was quite variable. We had to put them into some [meaningful] clusters but it was variable. It is a very good question, thanks!

[**Sunil Puria**]: Sriram, thanks. Brilliant presentation. The slides are very clear, I appreciate that. I think I am one of the people that can rumble. But I wanted to measure with a Laser Doppler Velocimeter (LDV). I think you have one now. That is what ear drum vibrations look like. Sound pressure level (SPL) is easier but measuring the eardrum vibrations would be cool.

[**Ernst Dalhoff, session chair**]: Especially at low frequencies.

[**Susan Voss**]: Really nice presentation. I too think I can rumble. My question is when I rumble, it is a very quick turn on/off. [For me,] I keep doing that during 2s. What effect would it have on subjects? Or, is it possible the length of time some people are rumbling is so short you are not capturing it, because when I am doing this, my Eustachian tube clearly opened but it is just on/off. I talked to somebody else and their rumbling lasts for many seconds. I am curious how that might affect things and if you asked your subjects that.

[**Sriram Boothalingam, author**]: Great question. Yes, we did ask. Some talk about this [rumbling] as clicking. I am guessing, it may be that the Eustachian tube opens and closes pretty rapidly. From us asking our participants, it seemed like they could, one way or the other, they could either turn it on or off or they could hold it. It looks like there are at least two separate types of people but in people like you they could leave it on/off but it is coming on and off. But it would be interesting to see what [Ondrej] suggested to put them into separate groups to see if there is anything different.

[**Jon Siegel, written comments**]: The ability to voluntarily contract one's middle ear muscles has always intrigued me since I can do it. I hear the rumble described in this paper and I'm curious that I never hear that when I'm not voluntarily inducing it, so if the muscle causing it (likely the tensor tympani) is active in other situations then there must be a reason why the "rumbling isn't heard. I was intrigued by the this paper for good reason. Inducing and measuring the effects of MEM contractions in the ear canal using click stimuli has been routine in studies from other groups, i.e., Feeney, Keefe, etc. But their methods are truly wideband, including the frequency range below 1 kHz

where the changes are the largest and perhaps the most significant for hearing if the primary role of the acoustic reflex is to reduce low-frequency masking noise. The present study used band-limited clicks that focused on the range of 0.89-4.2 kHz and the lowest 1/3 octave band of effects is centered at 1 kHz. It would be good to know why a wider bandwidth wasn't used. Also, the change in click stimulus pressure (including reflected pressure) is quantified, rather than the more common change in absorbance or power reflectance, so it's hard to relate these results to those of other studies. It would be helpful to be given a better understanding of this choice. The changes in the group of subjects are small and not generally consistent. Our own measurements of absorbance change above 1 kHz are also variable, but generally larger than shown here. Before we started measuring absorbance changes caused by the MEMR, we had used a measure of absolute pressure change normalized to the pressure with no elicitor as done by Wojtczak et al (2017). That measure was generally similar to absorbance change, but was much more noisy at low frequencies. Since the rumbling contraction is inherently noisy, is this a problem in itself? Is it a reason lower frequencies weren't studied?

[Sriram Boothalingam, author]: The answer to frequency choice is provided in response to Jon's session question. The magnitude of the change is small, likely in part because the stimulus at 85 dB ppSPL was scaled down to 55 dB ppSPL to be able to visualize changes in both stimuli on the same scale.

[Jon Siegel, written comments]: In the section "MEMR Estimation" why is it assumed that large changes must be seen at all frequencies analyzed? We've seen a lot of variability at higher frequencies in individuals in spite of consistently reduced absorbance below 1 kHz.

[Sriram Boothalingam, author]: We have removed this section to conserve space. We did not expect to see large changes at higher frequencies. Perhaps this refers to our expectation to see a present response to be considered a significant change. We did this to ensure we were not including spurious changes that sometimes occur. Such changes are typically not consistent across frequencies and levels. Considering we had 7 1/3rd octave bands and two levels, we used these to our advantage to ensure the changes we observed are consistent.

[Jon Siegel, written comments]: It's puzzling why no consistent effects were seen in Fig 5 [removed to conserve space] since both the stapedius and tensor tympani act to stiffen the middle ear. Might this be more apparent below 1 kHz?

[Sriram Boothalingam, author]: Yes, the effects observed here may be different below 1 kHz.

[Jon Siegel, written comments]: Cho and colleagues (2023) have shown that the TT has a larger effect than the stapedius at the umbo, so their results would suggest that the latter isn't dominant (at any frequency?).

[Sriram Boothalingam, author]: Thank you. Our conclusion of the SM dominating in the 1-4 kHz region is based on the observation that there is not much change to the reflex magnitude or kinetics when SM alone (nogo/85) is present vs. when SM+TTM (go/85) is present. Cho and colleagues (2023) data certainly seems to suggest larger TTM-induced changes at umbo and stapes. It would be interesting to compare acoustic and physical measurements in a single experiment to reconcile these results.

[Susan Voss, written comments]: This work strives to separate and understand the effects of the stapedius and tensor tympani muscles using live human subjects who can contract their tensor tympani muscles. It is an interesting experimental approach and I look forward to the discussion. Here are a few comments and questions.

1. The manuscript is more than twice the stated page limit. I double checked about this requirement with the organizers and was told it must be reduced to 6 pages or may not be published. There are many parts that perhaps could be summarized more succinctly and perhaps fewer references could be made.

2. Figure 2 is not discussed when it is first presented and perhaps both Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 could be eliminated to support the need to shorten the manuscript.

[Sriram Boothalingam, author]: Thank you. We have now reduced content to fit within the 6-page limit.

3. Overall, the changes with the tensor tympani contraction are very small and average to nearly zero. Did you repeat any of these measurements in a given subject? The changes are much less than 1 dB. It seems that a study of the variability and repeatability of these measurements in a given subject would be important.

[Sriram Boothalingam, author]: Thank you, yes, we should certainly conduct another test-retest study. However, we included a few objective markers in place to ensure the changes we are seeing are not spurious despite their small magnitude. (1) We fit a statistical model to the change data and test its significance using a permutation-based test,

(2) changes across frequencies and levels were compared to ensure the change we see are meaningful, e.g., a change for 55 dB ppSPL not replicated at 85 dB ppSPL, where one would expect to see a change, were not considered true changes, and (3) we only included changes that were consistent across 6 out of the 7 frequencies in addition to the above two criteria.

4. Is there a difference in asking a subject to contract their TT muscle vs. the TT involuntary contraction? Does the stapedius simply contract in response to loud sounds and hold its contraction until the sound is over? If so, does the TT do the same? How does this differ from a subject repeatedly contracting their TT? Some discussion of this issue might be helpful.

[Sriram Boothalingam, author]: Great question. We did not test the TT involuntary contraction. The SM contraction to loud sound and its decay over many seconds is well documented and used as the acoustic reflex decay test. In our conversations with our participants, majority of them say they can hold it for no more than 2-3 seconds. This is why our paradigm included a 2 second window to capture these effects. It would be interesting to investigate the TTM decay. Comparing sustained vs repeatedly constricting, i.e., turning this reflex on/off in very short intervals (<0.5s) would make for an interesting comparison. We, unfortunately, did not ask this question and therefore cannot separate these participants.

5. My take away from Fig. 5 is that voluntary contraction of the TT has essentially no effect on the pressure at the tympanic membrane ($< \pm 1$ dB). The abstract implies otherwise: “Our study revealed that the TT does indeed influence signal transmission through the middle ear”. Figure 5 seems to imply there are not systematic or possibly significant changes. Again, repeated measurements as well as a statistical analysis might be appropriate in order to draw this conclusion.

[Sriram Boothalingam, author]: Thank you. We have now softened this. We said this to indicate that the TTM does induce changes at the lower stimulus level (go/55) where the SM is not expected to be active, but this TTM effect does not seem to modulate the SM effects at higher stimulus level (go/85) where both TTM and SM are expected to be active. This is puzzling given the physical measurement data of Cho and colleagues (2023) and must be investigated further in future studies.